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Abstract

The aim of this report is to define a sound policy for human resource acquisition and management for the future E-RIHS ERIC. It aims at giving an overview of every aspects a research infrastructure should consider to create and implement the most adequate human resources policy adapted to its needs and ambitions.

The report describes the type of experts E-RIHS would need in its central office to achieve its missions and its objectives. For each key role the scope of responsibilities and the required skills set as well as the level of remuneration is detailed. The organisational structure of E-RIHS has been analysed as well. The structure of an organisation affects namely its ability to respond and adjust to change but it also has an impact on the motivation and commitment of the employees.

The report also tackles the different forms of employment used in ERICs and presents the alternative between direct employment and secondment, assessing their advantages and disadvantages. It also identifies and describes in details the main stages of the recruitment process as well as define a recruitment strategy. Hiring is an investment and good recruitment takes time. From anticipating the need to integrating the new employee, there are many steps in the hiring process

A research infrastructure should not only be able to attract and recruit good staff but, most importantly, retain its valuable personnel over time. As a consequence, the report reviews the different types of benefits and rewards the organisation can implement to be and stay attractive but also proposes motivation and engagement principles to address the needs and expectations of the employees.

Offering a rich and cohesive training program to the employees in order to develop their skills and competencies is extremely important for an organisation. The report shows how it helps the staff to respond and adapt to the different challenges that may occur in a research infrastructure.

Finally, the report identifies critical risks likely to have a negative impact on the human resources policy within E-RIHS and provides some thoughts and advices to mitigate those risks.

DISCLAIMER:

This document reflects the state of advancement of the preparatory work at the time of its delivery. As such, its content may be subject to further evolution.

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Abstract (for dissemination)	This document is intended to help defining a sound policy for human resource acquisition and management for E-RIHS.
Keywords	Human Resources, recruitment, remuneration, motivation, engagement, career building, risk mitigation

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Introduction

Building a successful ERIC requires, on the one hand, a unique and solid scientific project that meets the expectations of a large community of researchers and, on the other hand, well-designed support functions – administration, finance, human resources that help carry out the scientific activities. Therefore, setting up an adequate human resources policy is vital for realising the potential of a world-class research infrastructure. After all, people are at the heart of every successful organisation.

E-RIHS is the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science that supports research on heritage interpretation, preservation, documentation and management. E-RIHS entered the ESFRI Roadmap in 2016, and, with EHRI, is the only research infrastructure project in the Social and Cultural Innovation section of the Roadmap. It will comprise: E-RIHS Headquarters and National Hubs, fixed and mobile instruments in national infrastructures of recognized excellence, physically accessible collections and archives as well as virtually accessible heritage data. The ERIC status is expected to be granted in 2022¹.

The aim of this report is to help defining a sound policy for human resource acquisition and management for the future E-RIHS ERIC. It describes the type of experts required, including suggested skills and develops strategies for creating motivation, engagement and support career building. Moreover, the report considers organisation of work in E-RIHS central office, the recruitment process, different types of engagement for the ERIC, remuneration and benefits, rewards, training, mobility and employment termination. Finally, the report provides a tentative risk management structure concerning human resources activities.

The table below shows, in percentage, the amount of the total operating costs dedicated to cover personnel costs in several ERICs. From the initial financial planning, it is estimated² that personnel costs in E-RIHS should amount 46% of the total operating costs.

Image 1 - Ratio personnel costs over total operating costs of some ERICs

* not in operational phase at the moment of writing

¹ <http://www.e-rihs.eu/e-rihs-progress-state/>

² For the report, we used as a main reference the first outcomes of D3.1 Preliminary Financial Plan.

The above mention chart shows that personnel is an important part of the operating costs in most ERICs and therefore a key factor for the long-term sustainability of these organisations. A research infrastructure should not only be able to attract and recruit adequate scientific and administrative staff, but above all retain valuable personnel over the time. Ensuring that the right people are at the right place at the right time requires that external (adequate training programmes, mobility, greater harmonisation at EU level³) and internal factors are met. To achieve this goal, the human resources policy within an ERIC plays a crucial role. It is an extremely complex activity that should be planned and implemented with particular care. It concerns several activities can be summarised, even though not exhaustively, as follows:

- Recruiting and integration
- Training and staff development
- Secondments
- Performance appraisal
- Conflict management
- Advice to staff and supervisors
- Personnel administration
- Contracts
- Salary and benefits
- Negotiation of Agreements
- Social relations (e.g. unions)
- Work conditions
- Staff plan and costs
- Budget follow-up
- Information and communication
- Organisation
- Work legislation
- Policies and rules
- Welfare
- Other services (travels, food...)
- Staff engagement and motivation
- Mobility

Image 2 - Human resources activities, cit. from RAMIRI handbook

In order to draft the best possible human resources policy fitted for the future E-RIHS ERIC we have used several different sources. First of all, we used the experience we have gained the past five years in DARIAH as an operational ERIC. The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) was launched as an ERIC in 2014 and brings together 19 Member countries and more than 20 cooperating partners from all over Europe. We also adapted the knowledge gained through European Networks such as the ERIC Forum and RITrain, which both provided valuable insights on RI management, staff profiles, training, and competencies. Furthermore, we built on the results of the projects RAMIRI I⁴ and RAMIRI II⁵ (Realising and Managing International Research Infrastructures) funded by the FP7 programme. Finally, we reviewed the scientific literature to suggest best practises for an ERIC-oriented human resources management.

A first version of the deliverable was released in M24. As a result of the feedback we received, we have been able to improve the structure and content of this report and delivered its final version in M36. However, it should be underlined that a human resources policy is closely linked to the evolution of an organisation. E-RIHS is still in its construction phase and many factors that will influence its human resources policy are still uncertain. We hope that the report will be able to provide a solid basis for the future of the research infrastructure.

³ ESFRI Long-Term Sustainability Working Group (2017), Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures, Dipartimento di Fisica - Università degli Studi di Milano, p. 24.

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/90502/reporting/en>

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/98535/reporting/en>

1 Work organisation in E-RIHS

The mission of E-RIHS is to support research on heritage interpretation, preservation, documentation and management, to deliver integrated access to expertise, data and technologies through a standardized approach, and to integrate world-leading European facilities into an organisation with a clear identity and a strong cohesive role within the global heritage science community.

The mission statement clearly shows that, on the one hand, E-RIHS is a pan-European infrastructure composed of a headquarter and many national hubs, multiple labs with fixed and mobile instruments, in a nutshell a complex organisation with a foothold in many countries, building bridges between research institutions, employing people from all over Europe. On the other hand, the mission statement also points out the cohesive role of the central office which shall structure the multiple parts of this intrinsically complex organisation. Drawing a comprehensive human resources policy calls in first instance to focus on the structure of the central office, because of its pivotal role between the various stakeholders but also because the contact persons in the national hubs are first and foremost subject to the personnel policy of their home organisation.

1.1 Description of the key roles

The organisation of E-RIHS central office as conceived by the team behind the creation of the infrastructure has been found in three major documents:

- the Scientific and Technical Description⁶ ;
- the E-RIHS ERIC central activities⁷;
- the financial annex.⁸

According to the three documents and based on our understanding, the current central office structure foresees the following positions. At this point, it is important to note that both the employment structure and the number of employees can vary greatly depending on the budget that will be allocated to the ERIC, the strategic decisions or the development of the activity. This has a rather indicative value and reflects the vision of the infrastructure at a given point in time.

- **Director General**, who will assume the leading role of the organisation, define the strategy and represent E-RIHS on a European and international level;
- **Deputy directors**, they will second the Director General in specific functions;
- **Head of office**, who will manage the operations and the employees of the central office;
- **Head of unit “strategy”**, who will help the Director General in strategy related matters, with the primary goals of increasing membership and globalisation of the activities;
- **Head of unit “access”**, who will manage access to equipment, services. He or she will organise the calls and establish the link with the users;
- **Head of unit “international relations”**, who will make the link between European and international partners, organize events and training activities;

⁶ The Scientific and Technical Description, version: 20181015_ERIHS_STD_VO7.pdf

⁷ The E-RIHS ERIC central activities (Version 04 / August 06, AD 2018 / J-MM, LP, JS, MB, MS)

⁸ The financial annex (version: ERIHS_Financial_Annex_vs01.pdf)

- **Head of unit “communication”**, who will be in charge for the communication and dissemination of results and activities as well as public relations;
- **Head of unit “projects”**, who will develop and manage projects, support project proposals and explore activities related to external funding;
- **Head of unit “quality and risk”**, who will ensure the quality within E-RIHS and assess the risk;
- **Head of unit “Administration”**, who will be in charge of daily administrative functions and coordinate finance and accounting;

It is also understood that up to 6 assistants would second the different heads of unit in their role.

Finally, services such as IT, accounting, audit or legal consultants will be outsourced.

Based on this information and a desk study that identified the positions which are essential to run any research infrastructure, we have developed for each type of experts required to run optimally the future E-RIHS ERIC a list of job-specific responsibilities and the skills expected to perform the position.

1.2 Responsibilities and skills for each key role

In this section, we defined for each key role the responsibilities and the skill set needed for the position. From a practical point of view, this exercise will help write the job advertisements when the time comes.

DIRECTOR GENERAL

Regardless of the field of the ERICs under exam, the presence of a Director General/Executive Director/Scientific Director is, not surprisingly, common for almost all ERICs. The RAMIRI handbook defines the leading director as a “*well-known and respected person in the discipline who has ideally communicative skills, a broad overview of the field, charismatic character to convince researchers and technologists about joint programs and initiatives*”⁹. The director is both the face of the organisation to the outside world and its head, in the sense that it is his or her responsibility to decide on strategic issues. He might not always be involved in the operational details, he nevertheless bears responsibility for all the activities carried out by the research infrastructure, particularly from a legal point of view as he is its legal representative.

Responsibilities:

- Define the strategic development of the organisation;
- Develop and implement an action plan based on the strategy;
- Oversee all financial and budgeting issues;
- Be the legal representative of the organisation;
- Ensure the long-term sustainability of the organisation;
- Represent the organisation and build strong relationships with a broad range of stakeholders within and outside the consortium, at both European and international level;
- Ensure that activities comply with European and national regulations but also with ethical standard, and societal values;
- Monitor and assess the impact of the activities and report to General Assembly;
- Lead fundraising efforts;
- Monitor the adherence of the national consortia to the operational rules and standards of the organisation;
- Facilitate and support the activities of the governance bodies;
- Oversee the management of the personnel.

Skills:

- PhD or equivalent experience in science, business or engineering preferably in the field of the RI;
- Possess a strong scientific and research policy network both at international and EU level;
- Strategic competence;
- Experience in leading teams and consortia;
- Excellent communication and public relation skills;
- Relevant experience in the European research landscape and a good understanding of European research policy;
- Fundraising skills and experience;
- Leadership and managerial abilities;

⁹ <https://www.ceric-eric.eu/project/ramiri-handbook/chapter-5/>

DEPUTY DIRECTOR

Like the position of Director, the position of Deputy Director is common to many ERICs. It is also not uncommon to find several Deputy Directors within the same organisation, for example DARIAH has two of them, CLARIN three. They must have an excellent knowledge of the structure and are often specialized in a certain aspect of the activities: technology, finances, etc. They assist the Director in the decision-making process. If necessary, they may replace the Director in his or her role as representative of the organisation. In some organisations, the Director and the Deputy Directors are grouped under one governance body, the Board of Directors.

Responsibilities:

- Assist the Director in the strategic development of the organisation, particularly in the field under his or her responsibility;
- Develop and implement a work plan in the field under his or her responsibility;
- Assist the Director ensuring the long-term sustainability of the organisation;
- Build strong relationships with a broad range of stakeholders within and outside the consortium, at both European and international level;
- Ensure that activities comply with European and national regulations but also with ethical standard, and societal values;
- Monitor and assess the impact of the activities plan in the field under his or her responsibility;
- Oversee the management of the personnel in the field under his or her responsibility.

Skills:

- PhD or equivalent experience in science, business or engineering preferably in the field of the RI;
- Possess a strong scientific and research policy network both at international and EU level;
- Strategic competence;
- Expertise in the field under his or her responsibility
- Experience in leading teams and consortia;
- Excellent communication and public relation skills;
- Relevant experience in the European research landscape and a good understanding of European research policy and how relevant European institutions operate (ESFRI, Funding framework, etc.);
- Leadership and managerial abilities;

HEAD OF OFFICE

Another common position in research infrastructures is the head of the central office, which ensures the efficient and effective operations of the central office. Under the leadership of the Directors and the Deputy Directors, the Head of Office is responsible for managing the activities and the personnel of the central office on a daily basis. His or her mission is to ensure that the strategic action plan is properly implemented and that the different departments work together efficiently and effectively. He or she reports to the Director and the Deputy Director(s)

Responsibilities:

- Manage the personnel of the central office;
- Maintain oversight and coordinate the activities of the organisation;
- Prepare the budget and monitor the level of expenses for all department;
- Take organisational responsibility for the timely and effective liaison with all statutory bodies;
- Maintain and ensure compliance with the statutes, the internal rules of procedure and the different policies across the organisation, adapting them as needed;
- Act as a first point of contact for the Members, Observers, governing bodies of the organisation ensuring effective communication throughout the organisational structure;
- Moderate and support the discussion between - among others - EU project partners, representatives of national ministries, funding agencies and external partners;
- Ensure overall management tasks, including monitoring, reporting, risk management.

Skills:

- Master or equivalent experience in business administration or science, preferably in the field of the RI;
- Experience in managing teams;
- Experience in financial oversight of an organisation;
- Ability to conform with the deadlines and requirements of research infrastructure;
- Excellent knowledge of the European policy landscape with relation to research and research infrastructures;
- Excellent oral and written communication skills.

HEAD OF UNIT “STRATEGY”

The head of the strategic department shall help the Director in all strategic related matters, with the primary goals of increasing membership and globalisation of the activities. This position is not very common in research infrastructures; strategy planning falls under the prerogatives of the Director who is then assisted by one or more Deputy Directors. However, a well-defined strategy, translated into strategic action points is the corner stone of every successful organisation. It is even more relevant for organisation at the beginning of their existence. As a consequence, having a staff member whose role is to assist the Director in all strategic related issues appears to be an excellent solution.

Responsibilities:

- Assist the Director in defining the strategic development of the organisation;
- Help the Director translating the strategy in a concrete action plan;
- Monitor the implementation of the strategy and its impact;
- Identify Membership and partnership opportunities both at a European and worldwide level;
- Develop argumentation and documents to attract new Members;
- Identify the scientific needs and trends of the field to continuously develop the strategy.

Skills:

- Master or equivalent experience in business administration, engineering or science, preferably in the field of the RI;
- Excellent knowledge of the field at national, European and international level;
- Excellent analytical skills;
- Strategic thinking mindset;
- Excellent oral and written communication skills.
- Excellent interpersonal skills

HEAD OF UNIT “ACCESS”

The Head of the access department shall manage the access to equipment, services. He or she will organise the calls and establish the link with the users. Depending on the size and the budget of the research infrastructure as well as the number of access points to manage, this position can be found in some ERICs. Access is a central element of E-RIHS activities, it is therefore a key role for the organisation.

Responsibilities:

- Contribute to the overall access policy of E-RIHS;
- Develop a system to manage the calls, their reviews and assessment in accordance with the access policy;
- Act as a first contact point for the users;
- Develop good practices and documentation on access and user’s issues;
- Cooperate with all stakeholders involved to guarantee a fair access to the equipment defined by the access policy;
- Improve continuously the processes related to access.

Skills:

- Master or equivalent experience in science in the field of the RI;
- Excellent knowledge of the field at national, European and international level;
- Excellent knowledge of the equipment and access policy in the field;
- Excellent analytical skills;
- Project management skills;
- Excellent oral and written communication skills.

HEAD OF UNIT “INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS”

The head of the international relations department is expected to have a high-level experience in liaising with various stakeholders from multiple fields and has to have an excellent knowledge of the scientific context in which the organisation operates. The objective is to engage with stakeholders and/or industry related to the infrastructure, make the link between European and international partners, organise events and training activities. High-level lobbying towards, for example, the European Commission may also constitute an important part of the job.

Responsibilities:

- Engage with stakeholders related to the organisation;
- Identify and develop national/European/international partnerships;
- Assist the Director in preparing high-level meeting with various stakeholders;
- Advocacy and lobbying for the organisation;
- Support international outreach and partnering initiatives;
- Plan and organise events to promote the organisation;
- Develop training activities to attract researchers.

Skills:

- Master or equivalent experience in business administration, engineering or science, preferably in the field of the RI;
- High-level experience in liaising with various stakeholders;
- Excellent knowledge of the scientific context in which the organisation operates;
- Experience in building partnerships;
- Excellent oral and written communication skills;
- Excellent interpersonal skills.

HEAD OF UNIT “COMMUNICATION”

The role of communication officer is common to all ERICs. Develop a successful communication strategy, promote the activities of the organisation and engage with the research communities is essential for every research infrastructure. Communication is not just an activity directed outside the organisation, internal communication is also essential, particularly in a large distributed infrastructure such as E-RIHS. Communication encompasses a large number of tasks and activities on a day-to-day basis, so that, in many structures, more than one person is needed to carry them out.

Responsibilities:

- Assist the Director with the development of a communication, dissemination, exploitation and outreach strategy for the organisation;
- Set up the appropriate communications channels to ensure effective distribution of communication products and outputs across members’ countries and institutions;
- Decline the communication strategy through the various communication channels, e.g. via website, social media presence; newsletter; press kit, brochures, reports and strategy papers, flyers, events, etc.;
- Manage relations with service providers (graphic designer, printers, website maintenance...);
- Manage relations with the media;
- Write the annual report of the organisation.

Skills:

- Master or equivalent experience in business with specialization in communication or in science, preferably in the field of the RI with previous communication work. experiences;
- Have excellent oral and written communication skills;
- Excellent interpersonal skills;
- Be proficient with website management, databases, social media platforms and other relevant technologies;
- Understand how to communicate research results to the academic and general public;
- Excellent command of written and spoken English.

HEAD OF UNIT “PROJECTS”

The role of project manager is also very common in research infrastructures. He or she defines standard operating procedures for project management, plans and prepares project applications and coordinates work across partner organisations. The work of the project manager in an ERIC is very related to the European project funding programmes, i.e. Horizon 2020 at the present time and Horizon Europe starting next year. According to the volume of external funded projects, this position can be assisted by project-specific officers for the daily management. One of his or her task is also to explore activities related to external funding.

Responsibilities:

- Oversee the entire project lifecycle from the draft to the final report;
- Run the overall legal, contractual and administrative management of the agreement with the European Commission for EU projects;
- Coordination of the redaction of periodic technical reports of EU projects;
- Preparing financial reports and transfer to partners within EU projects;
- Support principal investigators in building and writing project proposals;
- Advice the Director/Head of Office/national nodes on potential funding opportunities;
- Manage the project team in case of numerous projects.

Skills:

- Master or equivalent experience in science or engineering, preferably in the field of the RI;
- Excellent knowledge of EU funding programmes and, in general, mode of operation of the European Union;
- Project management skills
- Organisational skills: ability to prioritise tasks and to meet deadlines
- Experience in management of EU funded projects;
- Budget expertise;
- Excellent oral and written communication skills;
- Excellent interpersonal skills.

HEAD OF UNIT “QUALITY AND RISKS”

The head of the quality and risks department shall be responsible for the quality of the services delivered within E-RIHS as well as of the processes in place. He or she shall be able to assess and prevent the eventual risks that the infrastructure could face. This position exists in some ERICs but is not very common. Nevertheless, given the importance of processes in E-RIHS (application, selection, peer review, etc.) and the numerous access points involved, it appears very sensible to have a person responsible to maximise the quality and transparency while diminishing the risks. If the future ERIC’s budget is not large enough to hire all the key functions as described here, we can envision that units “access” and “quality” merge because of the complementary of their roles.

Responsibilities:

- Develop a quality control and monitoring system;
- Elaborate good practices and documentation to improve quality within the organisation;
- Cooperate with all stakeholders involved to maintain the quality in the highest standards;
- Identify the potential risks to the organisation and report them to the director;
- Develop mechanisms and strategies to reduce risks and implement them.

Skills:

- Master or equivalent experience in business administration, engineering or science, preferably in the field of the RI;
- Excellent knowledge of the field at national, European and international level;
- Excellent analytical skills;
- Excellent knowledge of the processes in the field of the RI;
- Excellent oral and written communication skills.

HEAD OF UNIT “ADMINISTRATION”

The head of the administrative department shall be in charge of daily administrative functions and coordinate finance and accounting. He or she takes care of all secretariat tasks in the broadest sense of the term: management of the premises, keep track of the expenses, liaise with outsourced services such as accounting or auditing, etc. Depending on the size of the infrastructure, this role can be required one or more assistants to help with daily tasks such as making travel arrangements, etc.

Responsibilities:

- Ensure the overall smooth running of the central office, make sure that everyone has the means to do their job in the best possible conditions;
- Keep accurate records of all transactions and prepare the work for the accountant and the auditor;
- Process expenses in a timely manner;
- Help the Head of Office for the budget planning;
- Coordinate financial reports work across the difference department;
- Assist in event planning and coordination;
- Oversee travel arrangements.

Skills:

- Master or equivalent experience in business administration, engineering or science, preferably in the field of the RI;
- Knowledge in finance and accounting;
- Knowledge of national and ERICs legislation of VAT, tax and wages;
- Excellent analytical skills;
- Excellent organisation and comfortable with multitasking.

1.3 E-RIHS’s organisational structure

Each function and role within the organisation, no matter how well defined, does not operate independently of each other. Interactions between people are numerous and diverse in nature: hierarchical relationships, collaboration on a project, etc. In order to ensure that the organisation is as efficient and effective as possible, it is also necessary to consider the organisational structure in which people work. It affects the organisation's ability to respond and adjust to change but it also has an impact on the motivation and commitment of the employees. It is, of course, too early to make a review of the organisational structure of an organisation that does not yet exist. But it is nevertheless interesting to provide a brief analysis on the basis of the information available to us and to propose alternative approaches as food for thought.

From the key roles that have been identified in the above section, we have created a comprehensive organisational chart of the E-RIHS central office:

Image 3 - Suggested organisational chart of the central office¹⁰

The design of E-RIHS central office, as described above, is rather traditional: a top management, a hierarchic line and an operating core divided by departments. Following Mintzberg’s types of organisational structure¹¹, E-RIHS central office would be a *simple structure*: A generally small, relatively young organisation where the predominant coordination mechanism is mutual adjustment or direct supervision. The power is very centralized, the hierarchical line small. The most important component of the organisation is the strategic summit.

¹⁰ A more readable version of the chart can be found in the [Appendix 1](#)

¹¹ Mintzberg H. (1980) "Structure in 5's: A Synthesis of the Research on Organisation Design." *Management Science* 26, no. 3: 322-341.

Image 4 - Mintzberg's simple structure

In this type of structure “*power over all important decisions tends to be centralized in the hands of the chief executive officer (in our case the Director General)*”¹². The strategic apex is the key part of the structure and the operating core is “*organic*”, grouped into units structured on an often loose functional basis. “*Communication flows informally in this structure [...] decision making is informal, with the centralization of power allowing for rapid response*”¹³.

A *simple structure* has certain advantages: the organisation is organic, dynamic and often innovative. It’s the typical structure of entrepreneurial firm and in some ways an ERIC could be viewed as some sort of public research start-up. On the other hand, it has some disadvantages as well. It is very dependent on the director, who has tight control over the structure and this form of organisation “*tend to make the transition to bureaucracy as they age*”¹⁴.

1.4 Alternative forms of organisational structure

In an increasingly complex world, organisations are asked on the one hand to be competitive, flexible and always ready to adapt. Employees on the other hand strive for empowerment and look for a rich and meaningful work environment where they can both express their potential and aspirations. In this context, self-organisation, neural network-like organisations or holacracy (to cite only a couple of them) are sought-after forms of organisations, not only in the start-up world but also in larger and more complex organisations. Permanent innovation, co-evolution, decentralized decision-making, agility and employee engagement are the key features of such organisations. “*So we cannot wish political hierarchies away with fashionable words, but neither should we assume that hierarchy is a necessary organisational form. Other worlds are possible. That is to say, there are*

¹² Ibid.

¹³ Ibid

¹⁴ Ibid

plenty of places where we can often empirically document hierarchies, but this doesn't mean that all organizing must (and therefore should) be hierarchical".¹⁵

Example of the Holacracy

A holacracy is a governance structure characterised by a distribution of power among self-organizing groups, rather than the top-down authority in the typical hierarchical corporate culture model. Holacracy provides a flat management structure that distributes authority. The goal is to ensure that those responsible for completing the work have the authority to decide how that work should be carried out. The benefits are expected to be an improvement of agility, transparency, accountability, employee engagement and innovation. These are the key shifts between a traditional organisation structure and holacracy:

Traditional organisation structure	Holacracy
Static job descriptions	Dynamic roles
Delegated authority	Distributed authority
Large scale re-organisation	Rapid iteration
Alignment with politics	Transparent rules

Contrary to a hierarchical organisation, here is how looks the work organisation within holacracy:

Image 5 - Work organisation in Holacracy

¹⁵ Parker M. (2012), Super Flat: Hierarchy, Culture and Dimensions of Organizing, in Reinventing Hierarchy and Bureaucracy – from the Bureau to Network Organisations, Emerald Group Publishing Limited.

Holacratic organisations ratify a constitution—a living document outlining the rules by which circles are created, changed, and removed. The circles don't just manage themselves; within those guidelines, they also design and govern themselves. The constitution doesn't say how people should do their tasks, it explains how circles should form and operate, how roles are identified and assigned, what boundaries the roles should have, and how the circles should interact. Leadership is distributed among roles and not individuals. It keeps changing as teams create and define new roles.

In the article “Beyond the Holacracy Hype”, published in 2016 in the Harvard Business Review, the authors highlight that *“using self-management principles to design an entire organisation makes sense if the optimal level of adaptability is high”*. Most organisations should adopt these techniques in part, *“not in a whole”*. It is for every organisation to evaluate *“how much hierarchy and process they need to ensure coherence”*. Finally, they conclude on the idea that *“the next generation of self-managing teams is demanding a new generation of leaders—senior individuals with the vision to see where it is best to set aside hierarchy for another way of operating, but also with the courage to defend hierarchy where it serves the institution's fundamental goals.”*¹⁶

¹⁶ Bernstein E., Bunch J., Canner N., Lee M., (2016), Beyond the Holacracy Hype, Harvard Business Review.

2 Usual forms of employment in existing ERICs

The implementation phase of an ERIC which corresponds to the first five years following its creation is delicate on many levels. This initial period is often characterised by the need of finalising and best-tuning services and access offers, attracting users and developing projects while striving for financial sustainability of the infrastructure. It is also at this time that an adequate human resources policy must be put in place which, on the one hand, makes it possible to attract talent from all over Europe and to secure the positions that are essential for the infrastructure, while at the same time allowing a certain degree of flexibility in order to react to fluctuations in activity and infrastructure needs.

The European Commission, when describing the status of the staff working for an ERIC, asserts the following: *“In national sites of distributed ERICs, staff employed by the members may be involved in the ERIC activities without any change in their employment status. Staff may also be seconded by the members to the ERIC. An ERIC may also recruit its own staff. The employment contracts will generally be governed by the law of the country in which staff is undertaking its activities.”*¹⁷

The status of people working in ERICs can be multiple and depends on many factors such as location of employment, being part of a project limited in time, etc. An ERIC may use the following legal and organisational models of engagement to cover its staffing or expertise needs:

- Employment contracts
 - Permanent employment contract
 - fixed-term contract
- Secondment
- Service Agreement
- Consulting

2.1 Employment contract

The first option is that the ERIC recruits its own staff. While it may seem obvious, several ERICs did or do not directly employ all or part of their staff. We can cite here DARIAH, CLARIN or SHARE. For an infrastructure, especially at the beginning of its existence, it may seem easier to second its staff, notably when the infrastructure is based and has staff in several countries. Being an employer means knowing and understanding the requirements of labour laws in each of them, from contract legal requirements to payments of taxes, social insurances and pensions. However, what is gained in convenience is lost in control. Indeed, employing its staff directly enables the development of a sound human resources policy adapted to the needs of the infrastructure where many levers can be used to increase efficiency or motivation, for example.

Employment contracts offer also full control over the work time and content of a position and bind the employees directly to the ERIC. Being an employer is not only about being able to sign an employment contract but far more about implementing a global human resources policy that can benefit both the organization and the employees, being able to attract talents, foster motivation or promote diversity. We will address the topics of commitment and motivation later in this document but to give an example, being an employer allows the creation of benefit plans for employees (additional pension schemes, education grants, health packages, bonuses, etc.).

¹⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/index.cfm?pg=eric-faq>

It must be stressed that while being an employer has many advantages, it also costs time and money. More efforts in HR management are required, in terms of staff regulations, recruitment policies, insurance, payrolls, but also to develop successful employee career paths and perspectives, etc. The entry cost is quite high: a lawyer should be consulted to prepare model employment contracts, the payroll might be outsourced as it required a very specific expertise, etc.

There are two types of employment contracts: permanent and fixed-term ones. As a general rule, employment contracts shall follow the national laws of the country in which the staff is employed. Therefore, limitations and constraints may arise from national labour and social security laws. While the permanent contract can be considered as the standard contract, it is not uncommon for a research infrastructure to offer time-limited contracts for a number of reasons. It is worth recalling that in the European Union only 13%¹⁸ of employees have a fixed-term contract. However, the levels differ significantly from country to country. The considerable differences between EU Member States in the propensity to use fixed-term employment contracts could be explained, at least to some extent, by national practices, labour supply and demand, employers' forecasts of growth or contraction in activity, and the ease with which they can recruit and dismiss staff.

A research infrastructure may have recourse to fixed-term contracts for one of the following reasons:

- replacing an employee who is absent or whose contract is suspended (parental leave, sick leave, etc.).
- temporary increase in the organisation's activity, e.g. participation in a European project

Fixed-term contracts are particularly indicated for funded projects, which implies a defined time-frame for delivering tasks. On a side note, in Horizon 2020 projects, personnel costs under classical employment contracts are eligible for reimbursement as “direct personnel costs”.

However, attention should be paid to the legal framework of the country in which the activity is carried out (or of the country employing the person in case of expatriation). National legislation may limit the length or number of possible successive fixed-term contracts. In another countries, the number of time-limited contracts cannot exceed a certain percentage of permanent contracts.

2.2 Secondment

As briefly mentioned in the above section, seconding personnel has advantages and disadvantages and can be used for all or part of the employees, be limited in time or used in a long-term perspective.

Pros:

- No need to set up an employment structure;
- Cost are lower than regular employment contract on the short term;
- No need for a specific knowledge of the national legal framework, particularly interesting when the infrastructure is implanted in several countries;
- HR management requires less efforts;
- Strengthen the relationship with the institution that seconds the personnel.

¹⁸ Source Eurostat, as a % of employees aged 20-64 in 2018

Cons:

- Knowledge management and team building are difficult to achieve;
- In certain cases, employees may have the feeling of being excluded from core activities;
- Building up a sound HR policy is difficult since leverage are de facto limited;
- No sense of a cohesive organisation culture;
- Framework agreements shall be created and maintained over the time;
- Secondment are often limited in time: the actual employer might be reluctant to offer a permanent contract to a person working for another organisation due to restrictive national regulation.

Secondments are widely used by ERICs and can be of two different types:

- **Against payment:** the employee has an employment contract with a third institution, which can be either part of the network or not. The ERIC reimburses the cost of the employer to the third party. Formally, seconded personnel are supervised by and bound to the human resources policy of the third institutions. However, the day-to-day supervision is concretely exercised by the ERIC. Usually, to cover overheads (rent, insurance, office equipment etc.), an additional amount on top of the total personnel cost (often between 10 to 25 % on top of the personnel cost) may be paid by the ERIC.
- **In-kind:** for secondments in-kind, the value of the secondment is recorded as part of the in-kind contributions of the Member State(s) in which the personnel are seconded.

In both cases, a good practise is to set up a framework agreement with the hosting institution.

In terms of secondment practice, the example of DARIAH is rather interesting. While its statutory seat is in Paris, DARIAH personnel is or has been seconded from four different institutions: Centre Marc Bloch e.V. in Berlin, Data Archiving Network Service in the Hague, Trinity College in Dublin and the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique in Paris. At its inception in 2014, DARIAH only had 1¹⁹ seconded employee (excluding the 3 part-time Directors), whereas at the end of 2019, DARIAH had a staff of 12 persons²⁰. 6 of them are seconded and 6 of them are directly employed by DARIAH ERIC. DARIAH became namely an employer for the first time in September 2019, in only one location, Berlin Germany, out of the four where DARIAH central administration is implanted.

2.3 Service Agreement

A service agreement is a form of contract between a service provider and the research infrastructure. The former commits to deliver a service or a set of services in certain conditions specified in the contracts (i.e. quality, accessibility, etc) for a certain period of time in return for payment²¹. In most of the case, the service is provided by a moral person, i.e. a research institution or a private company. Contrary to an employment contract, a service agreement isn't regulated by the labour law of a country but falls under commercial regulation. Generally, a service agreement extends over a long period of time, which is not the case for a consulting contract. Besides, a service

¹⁹ 1 full-time employee

²⁰ For a 9,2 FTE (full-time equivalent)

²¹ It is to be noted that a large number of services provided to ERICs as in-kind contributions are subject to a service agreement.

agreement doesn't specify how the service is produced or who is performing the service but stipulates the nature of the service and the quality of the results. Research infrastructures used this form of employment to outsource some of the tasks they need to perform without having sufficient knowledge or capacity to do it internally. Accounting or auditing are concrete example of activities subject to a service agreement used by many research infrastructures. The accounting or auditing firm is employed for a relatively long period of time (in France, where DARIAH has its statutory seat, the law prescribes a mandate period of 5 years) and is expected to deliver yearly balance sheets and audit reports according to the national rules in place. The details about how and who perform the service is generally not included in the agreement.

2.4 Consulting

A research infrastructure may use consulting services to solve a specific problem or to receive advice on a given issue. The consultant's work is generally limited in time and occurrence, even if the provided service can be divided into several sessions. The consulting firm or the consultant's service is not generally subject to a contract, a simple quotation will be presented to the research infrastructure prior to the service including the description of the service and its price. An invoice will be sent once the service has been performed.

Research infrastructures usually use consultants for ad hoc problems where they do not have in-house expertise or manpower capacity to resolve it. The employment relationship is very light and falls into the commercial regulation of a country. Such a relationship can be terminated at every moment without the need of an explanation. While this form of commitment is not as binding as an employment contract, it is much more expensive.

3 Recruitment process

Recruitment is a strategic issue for any organisation as the capital represented by human resources is essential. Recruiting requires time and a specific skill set. If small organisations usually don't have the resources to either have their own human resources department or outsource the task to a recruitment agency, they need nonetheless to hire the right person that would meet its needs. It is important for them to identify and understand the main stages of the recruitment process as well as define a recruitment strategy. Hiring is an investment and good recruitment takes time. From anticipating the need to integrating the new employee, there are many steps in the hiring process, which should all be carefully planned. The recruitment process follows these 5 steps:

- Step 1 – Recruitment strategy: developing the recruitment strategy and the attractiveness of the organization
- Step 2 – Preparing the recruitment: analyse of the needs and job description
- Step 3 – Finding the right candidates: job announcement and search for candidates
- Step 4 – Selection of applicants: initial screening and interviews
- Step 5 – Welcome and integration

3.1 Recruitment strategy and attractiveness of the organisation

In the current European context, research infrastructures need to rethink their recruitment policies and adopt best practices. They operate in a competitive environment, where each research institution strives to attract and recruit the best candidates. As a result, incorporating a recruitment component into the global strategy of the organisation is essential.

Young people and talents of all ages have and will have more and more job opportunities. Attracting highly sought-after candidates, seducing them, convincing them to choose your organisation becomes a necessity. A good external and internal image is a prerequisite for attracting, integrating and retaining the desired skills. Consistency between internal and external image is fundamental, the external image should be in line with internal practices. In that respect, each employee is an ambassador. He or she contributes to the construction of the organisation's image. The following practices contribute to raise the attractiveness of an organisation:

- Know the expectations of the future employees in their diversity. A researcher, a young graduate or a senior manager have different interests and aspirations, which need to be identified to define the right internal policies and practises.
- Have an appropriate communication on recruitment: promote the benefits of the organization, the career opportunities, etc.
- Identify recruitment pools (universities, specific training and education tracks, etc.) engage the people through events, workshops... and sustain the relationship

3.3 From recruitment need to job description

It is the employer's responsibility to identify recruitment needs. These needs are either a response to a change of the environment in which the organisation operates or a response to an occasional shortage of personnel.

Change in the organisation's environment can be caused by internal and/or external factors. In the case of E-RIHS, external factors could be for example: the introduction of new European regulations; the evolution of technologies or a decline of the budget dedicated to research at the national or European level. Internal factors are more common because directly related to the performance of an organisation. For E-RIHS, it could be the acquisition of new members or partners; restructuring the organisation or offering new services.

Each organisation regularly experiences movements within its staff that might trigger recruitment needs: reduction in working time, resignation, maternity/parental leave, dismissal, death, etc. In this context, the employer must decide whether or not he wants to address these recruitment needs.

Because a recruitment procedure required time, it's important to anticipate the changes both in the environment and in the current staff. If certain requirements are met, i.e. in terms of finance or timing, the employer should decide whether to initiate an internal selection procedure or external recruitment. Just like an external recruitment procedure, an internal procedure must follow certain rules. Fairness and transparency are important engagement factors, especially if multiple internal candidates apply for the same position.

For external recruitment, it is essential for an organisation to precisely describe what are the actual needs and what are the requirements and skills a person should have to address those needs. In concrete terms, the employer should write down:

- The job description: What are the actual tasks, the responsibilities, the challenges? What is the environment, the collaboration with other departments?
- The minimum requirement to fulfil the position: level of education, years of experience, knowledge of the field, will to travel, etc.
- The skills expected to assume the position: social and relational skills, languages, technical skills, etc.

3.4 Job announcement and channels of communication

Once the job description, the minimum requirements and the expected skills for the open position have been identified, the next step is to finalize the job offer that will be communicate and disseminate to the outside world. A job offer should include the following information:

- The job title;
- The name of the organisation that will employ the person (in case of secondment agreement, the relationship between the organisation for which the person will work and the actual employer should be clarified);
- The exact address where the person will work;
- A description of the organisation (context, vision, mission, activities, etc.);

- The duration of the contract. If there is a probationary period, it should be clearly indicated. If the contract can be eventually extended, it should be also written, i.e. “with possible prolongation”;
- The foreseen starting date of the employment;
- The salary range, depending on experience and qualification;
- The job description;
- The responsibilities;
- The minimal requirements;
- The expected skills;
- The application procedure, including a closing date for application, types of documents to submit, (i.e. a cover letter, a resumé, eventually references, etc.) in which format (i.e. all documents in one pdf file), an email address where to send the file and a contact person if there is any question;
- A description of the selection process: confirmation of application receipt by email, time slot for interviews, duration of the selection process, eventually composition of the recruitment committee;
- A mention about “equal opportunities policy”, for instance “E-RIHS is an equal opportunities employer and is committed to the employment policies, procedures and practices which do not discriminate on grounds such as gender, marital status, family status, age, disability, race, religious belief, sexual orientation or membership of the travelling community.”

Depending on the location of the employment, it is important to check if the form and content of the job offer is ruled by national laws and if it is the case, to comply with them.

Once the job announcement has been written, it should be communicated. The question is which channel of communication should the organisation choose to attract the fittest persons for the job.

- Word of mouth: the most ancient but in some respects the most efficient way to communicate. In this case, it is important to establish internal transparency, so that current employees and eventually stakeholders can spread the word among their acquaintances and contacts;
- Websites: the job offer shall be visible and accessible through the website of the organisation, as well as cooperating research institutions, for example in the national nodes and eventually on other relevant websites specialized in job offers.
- Newsletter: If the organisation has a newsletter, the job offer shall be communicated through this channel;
- Mailing lists: the organisation should identify mailing lists (not only its own) related to sector, disciplines (in case of E-RIHS: archaeology, heritage science...), etc. where the job offer might trigger interest;
- Social media (depending on the ones the organisation uses): Twitter, Facebook and the most suitable for that kind of announcement, LinkedIn;
- EURAXESS is an initiative of the European Commission delivering information and support services to professional researchers. Job offers in the research field can be posted on the EURAXESS website.

The job offer should be disseminated at least a month before the closing date for the application. A reminder shall be sent regularly through the mailing lists and the social media. To evaluate whether

or not the communication has been successful, an organisation should not consider the number of applications received but rather the quality and relevance of them.

3.5 From paper application to job interview: good practices

All the applications received should be acknowledged and centralized in one place. It means that each applicant would receive an email in which the organisation, here E-RIHS, confirms that the application has been successfully received, while at the same time reminding the applicant about the timeline of the selection procedure. At this stage, it might be relevant to check if the application is complete, namely if all the required documents has been sent. If not to contact the applicant so that he or she can correct his or her mistake.

Depending on the position, the recruiter may choose to form a selection committee which will review the applications and interview the candidates. In some organisations, the composition of the selection committee is strictly regulated by internal rules or guidelines. If there are none, it might be interesting to constitute an ad hoc committee. In the case of E-RIHS, the selection committee should be composed by the Director General (if not available, a Deputy Director could replace him or her), the Head of Office, the head of the unit in which the position is available and, if relevant and possible, an expert of the field (from one of the national nodes for example).

Once the application deadline is over, all the applications should be sent promptly to the selection committee for review. Ideally, members of the selection committee should review each application through an evaluation template and select the top three or four applicants for an interview. After each member has reviewed all the applications, the selection committee shall meet and discuss the choices they have made and reach a consensus around three or four applicants that will be interviewed.

Invitations to the selected candidates should be send at least ten days before the interview. The invitation should specify the time and place of the interview (if the interview is done by videoconference, the connection details should be provided), the composition of the selection committee that will be running the interview and eventual what the candidate should prepare for the interview (i.e. a presentation, a paper, etc.).

Prior to the interview, the selection committee shall agree on a certain number of questions that will be asked to each candidate in the same order, so that all applicants will be treated equally.

During the interview, each candidate should have more or less the same amount of time to introduce him or herself and answer the set of questions created by the selection committee. Interviews should be conducted in a professional and polite way. All questions on personal situation such as family status, health condition, sexual orientation, ethnic background, religion, political opinion or union membership are strictly prohibited.

Once a candidate has been chosen – an evaluation template might eventually help to assess the quality of the interviews – and he or she has accepted the job, the unlucky candidates shall be promptly notified that their applications were unsuccessful.

Within the framework of the GDPR, it is important to note that the unsuccessful applications cannot be stored in a repository – in case the organisation wants to keep them for later use – without the explicit consent of the candidate.

3.6 Welcome and integration

In order for the newcomer to feel quickly integrated into the organisation, to have all the practical and general information that will enable him or her to accomplish his or her mission, it is useful to set up a welcome procedure. Within the framework of E-RIHS, it could be set up as follows:

- Visit of the premises and individual introduction of the newcomer to colleagues;
- Presentation of the office, the workstation together with the handover of equipment (laptop, etc.) and the necessary identifiers for connection to the different software solutions and platforms used by E-RIHS;
- Information on practical details: security, access to the premises, use of common areas, etc.
- Information on working hours, teleworking, payroll, health insurance, any administrative work-related information;
- Handover of a set of documents including the overall presentation of E-RIHS (vision, mission, objectives, history, etc.), the organisation chart of the central office and the structuring of the national nodes, the statutes, the IRPs, the activity reports of the last two years and any other document that could be useful to understand the purpose and structure of the organisation.

In addition, the line manager, usually the Head of Office, should be responsible for supporting and advising the newcomer during the adaptation period. He or she will help the newcomer to solve any practical or psychological problems he or she may encounter. The line manager should introduce him or her to the ins and outs of the new job and provides all the necessary documentation to help him or her do it. The line manager should put him or her in contact with all the people with whom he or she will be working. The line manager should remain at the disposal of the newcomer for any help or advice, as long as necessary.

3.7 Promoting diversity, including gender equality

Promoting diversity can be a legal requirement of the country in which the organisation is located, but it is above all a social and moral priority of any modern organisation. Promoting diversity can take many forms, in the present case however, it concerns the recruitment process. This means that for equal competences, priority should be given to a person belonging to a discriminated group. This rule should not only be written in the job offer but also taken into consideration when reviewing the applications and interviewing the candidates.

Promoting diversity should not only be referred to when hiring someone through a small paragraph in the job offer but, much more, be at the core of the organisation's values and operation. It could be integrated in the internal rules of procedure in a specific section addressing how the organisation acts in concrete terms to foster diversity. The internal rules of procedure should also make sure that any discrimination related to gender, marital status, family status, age, disability, race, ethnic group, religious belief, sexual orientation will not be tolerated and severely sanctioned.

Besides, an employee of the organisation could be designated (through an elective process for instance) to be in charge of equality and fight against discrimination. Every person within the organisation can submit a complaint to this representative, who will bring it to the direction. The representative can also take actions within the organisation to foster good practices: gender-inclusive writing, code of conduct, etc.

The premises of the organisation must be adapted to accommodate people with disabilities with particular attention to building access, workstation, toilets, etc.

In general, gender equality should be implemented not only in the central office but most of all within the direction and all governance bodies: General Assembly, Scientific Board, etc.

4 Remuneration

There is a wide range of forms of remuneration. Remuneration is not limited to a fixed salary alone, but includes a wide variety of collective and individual, fixed and variable, immediate and deferred, monetary and in-kind components. An effective remuneration policy is based on a judicious combination of forms of remuneration:

- Annual base salary, which constitutes the fixed part and the guarantee of remuneration
- Bonus or variable compensation
- Peripheral benefits in-kind or not (i.e. additional healthcare, complementary pension scheme, financial support for transportation, housing, etc.)

The aim is to put in place the combination that best suits E-RIHS' strategy, organizational culture, management style and the needs and expectations of its employees.

4.1 Level of remuneration

The 2018 ESFRI Roadmap counts 18 ESFRI projects and 37 ESFRI landmarks. The current research infrastructure landscape is composed nowadays of 21 ERICs. In its report on long-term sustainability of research infrastructures²², the ESFRI wrote *“At all levels staff mobility and exchange programmes for project management and capacity building should be developed for RI personnel aided by greater harmonisation across countries of career paths, pension schemes and salaries [...]”*. However, no common threads of remuneration of ERICs employees have been established so far. The main reason is that the structure of salaries is nation-dependent and ERICs rely on their own standards, which are based on European or international practices or bound to national salary scales, or, in case of secondment agreements, aligned with standards applied by the seconding organisation.

The methodology used to determine remuneration levels for each type positions in this preliminary report is the following:

- Desk study on ERICs recent vacancies;
- Comparison of remunerations in research organisations and between civil servants in different European countries.

Concerning the first point, open positions which disclosed remunerations offered by ERICs in 2017 and 2018 have been analysed. As noted above, there are no studies or surveys available that indicates average salary policies applied by ERICs. Moreover, it is sensitive information that is not made available to the public, therefore little information was collected, only when a position was advertised.

To begin with, in accordance with the document “Financial annex” of September 24, 2018 the level of remuneration for E-RIHS central office has been calculated for five different positions: Director General, Deputy Director, Head of office, Head of unit and Assistant. The budget calculated for the personnel costs of the central offices is as follows:

²² Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures, European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures, Long-Term Sustainability Working Group, 2017

	Director General	Deputy director	Head of office	Head of unit	Assistant
FTE (full time equivalent)	1	0,5	1	1	1
Number of unit	1	4	1	7	6
Gross salary + employer's contribution (30%)	130 000 €	62 500 €	90 000 €	60 000 €	30 000 €
total	130 000 €	250 000 €	90 000 €	420 000 €	180 000 €
<i>That means a gross salary of</i>	<i>100 000 €</i>	<i>48 100 €</i>	<i>69 300 €</i>	<i>46 200 €</i>	<i>23 100 €</i>

It should be noted that the figures given by the budget were understood as complete personnel cost: it is to say the gross salary and the employer's contributions. The amount of employer's contributions varies in Italy depending on the region, the sector, the gross salary, etc. For this preliminary paper an average of 30% has been considered, however it should be refined at a later point for a finer analysis of the personnel costs.

In order to compare the level of remuneration for E-RIHS staff members with other ERICs and research institutions, an evaluation of the gross salary as been calculated. The table hereafter compares the level of remuneration of E-RIHS to different ERICs (mostly for the position of Director general), research and education organisations

	Director General	Deputy director	Head of office	Head of unit	Assistant	Comments
full time equivalent	1	1	1	1	1	
E-RIHS	100 000 €	96 200 €	69 300 €	46 200 €	23 100 €	<i>Calculation with 30% employer's contribution</i>
DARIAH ERIC	75 600 €		57 500 €	53 600 €		<i>Director level is an estimate based on the financial compensation wired to the institution employing the director minus 30% employer's contribution, Head of unit is an average (Berlin)</i>
CNR	56-100 k€	44-75 k€	34-56 k€	37 k€	26 k€	<i>gross salary depending on experience and negotiation for Liv. I, II, III DG=Liv.I, DD=Liv.II, HO=Liv.III, HU= Liv.IV, A=Liv.VII</i>
Trinity College	115-145 k€	88-118 k€	80-103 k€	57-89 k€	27-42 k€	<i>gross salary depending on negotiation and experience (scale?) DG=senior administrative 1/full professor, DD= sa2, HO=sa3, HU=admin 1, A=executive officer</i>
United Nation	111-140k€	95-120 k€	61-100 k€	47-77 k€	37-54 k€	<i>gross salary DG=D1, DD=P5, HO=UN Rome Italy level 6, HU= level 4, A= level 1</i>
Dutch public service	88-117 k€	74-97 k€	60-73 k€	32-50 k€	22-31 k€	<i>gross salary DG=18, DD=16, HO=13, HU= 10, A= level 1</i>
EMBRC ERIC	from 100 k€					<i>gross salary depending on negotiation and experience</i>
ANAE	120-150 k€					<i>strives to become an ERIC, total costs depending on experience 120-150k€, means 6724€ net salary for 150k€ costs</i>
CLARIN	77 -122 k€					<i>gross salary (for Professor)</i>
BBMRI ERIC	from 100 k€					<i>gross salary depending on negotiation and experience</i>
EMSO ERIC	100-130 k€					<i>gross salary depending on negotiation and experience</i>
LIBER				36-58 k€		<i>gross salary depending on negotiation and experience</i>
Private sector Italy (Toscana)	97 123 €	97 123 €	52 126 €	30 334 €	24 933 €	<i>Regional (Tuscany) average salary (private sector), 2017 (@Job Pricing 2018) / Dirigenti: 97.123€, Quadri: 52.126€, Impiegati: 30.334€, Operai: 24.933€</i>

Image 6 - Levels of remuneration

Besides, we analysed a study conducted by the SEO Amsterdam Economics in 2017 titled “Comparing the remuneration at international organisations with that at national governments”²³ which used 11 different reference persons²⁴ in total, who differ by age and job level, to compare civil servants’ annual average gross wages in international organisations (OECD-Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, NATO-North Atlantic Treaty Organisation, CoE-Council of Europe, EC-European Commission and UN United Nation) and those applied by selected national governments (France, Germany, Netherlands).

This study proved to be of particular interest in determining the level of remuneration that could be set for E-RIHS, not only because it takes into account salaries in various major international organisations and in the government of three major countries, but also because it takes into account employees in different positions at different points in their careers

	30 years old	40 years old	58 years old
Secretary	1 Spouse: No Children: No	2 Spouse: Yes Children: Aged 8 and 10	3 Spouse: Yes Children: Aged 26 and 28
Supporting policy officer	4 Spouse: No Children: No	5 Spouse: Yes Children: Aged 8 and 10	6 Spouse: Yes Children: Aged 26 and 28
Policy maker	7 Spouse: No Children: No	8 Spouse: Yes Children: Aged 8 and 10	9 Spouse: Yes Children: Aged 26 and 28
Head of unit		10 Spouse: Yes Children: Aged 8 and 10	11 Spouse: Yes Children: Aged 26 and 28

Image 7 - Overview of personal characteristics of the reference persons

Source: SEO analysis

Image 8 - Average Annual Gross Wages in selected international organisations and national governments

²³ Comparing the remuneration at international organisations with that at national governments, Siemen van der Werff, Valentijn van Spijker, for SEO Amsterdam Economics, 2017

²⁴ “The reference persons are 30, 40 and 58 years old, and they are all assumed to have been working at their current organisation since the age of 30. This implies that the 30-year-old reference persons are newly hired employees and the others are not. The job levels or positions are secretary officer (with an education at higher vocational level), supporting policy officer (with an education at bachelor level), policy maker (with an education at master level) and head of unit”.

Reference person	Employer	Gross wage		Tax and social security contribution	Benefits and allowances (net)	
		Gross salary	Gross family allowance		Family and children's allowance	Expat allowance
1	NL	€ 24,863	€ 0	-€ 4,665	€ 0	€ 0
	DE	€ 32,352	€ 0	-€ 6,366	€ 0	€ 0
	FR	€ 20,235	€ 0	-€ 3,222	€ 0	€ 0
	OECD	€ 27,479	€ 0	-€ 124	€ 0	€ 0
	CoE	€ 28,247	€ 0	-€ 121	€ 0	€ 0
	NATO	€ 31,880	€ 0	-€ 1,116	€ 0	€ 0
	EC	€ 24,885	€ 0	-€ 3,301	€ 0	€ 0
	UN	€ 31,485	€ 0	-€ 6,818	€ 0	€ 0
2	NL	€ 32,978	€ 0	-€ 4,839	€ 1,732	€ 0
	DE	€ 38,193	€ 4,511	-€ 5,599	€ 4,761	€ 0
	FR	€ 21,217	€ 813	-€ 2,212	€ 0	€ 0
	OECD	€ 35,719	€ 0	-€ 161	€ 9,349	€ 0
	CoE	€ 33,542	€ 0	-€ 144	€ 8,301	€ 0
	NATO	€ 41,247	€ 0	-€ 1,444	€ 9,606	€ 0
	EC	€ 31,856	€ 0	-€ 4,381	€ 22,650	€ 0
	UN	€ 43,551	€ 0	-€ 9,697	€ 1,568	€ 0
3	NL	€ 37,305	€ 0	-€ 8,433	€ 0	€ 0
	DE	€ 46,968	€ 1,704	-€ 7,649	€ 0	€ 0
	FR	€ 26,744	€ 0	-€ 3,501	€ 0	€ 0
	OECD	€ 41,872	€ 0	-€ 188	€ 2,776	€ 0
	CoE	€ 43,099	€ 0	-€ 185	€ 2,857	€ 0
	NATO	€ 46,321	€ 0	-€ 1,621	€ 3,071	€ 0
	EC	€ 46,140	€ 0	-€ 7,163	€ 3,090	€ 0
	UN	€ 49,569	€ 0	-€ 11,280	€ 1,568	€ 0
4	NL	€ 32,233	€ 0	-€ 8,021	€ 0	€ 0
	DE	€ 39,582	€ 0	-€ 8,908	€ 0	€ 0
	FR	€ 22,324	€ 0	-€ 3,676	€ 0	€ 0
	OECD	€ 31,555	€ 0	-€ 142	€ 0	€ 0
	CoE	€ 32,434	€ 0	-€ 139	€ 0	€ 0
	NATO	€ 35,405	€ 0	-€ 1,239	€ 0	€ 0
	EC	€ 28,381	€ 0	-€ 3,843	€ 0	€ 0
	UN	€ 35,003	€ 0	-€ 7,662	€ 0	€ 0
5	NL	€ 46,838	€ 0	-€ 11,661	€ 1,732	€ 0
	DE	€ 47,725	€ 4,511	-€ 8,274	€ 4,761	€ 0
	FR	€ 24,986	€ 936	-€ 2,756	€ 0	€ 0
	OECD	€ 40,577	€ 0	-€ 183	€ 9,670	€ 0
	CoE	€ 38,905	€ 0	-€ 167	€ 8,656	€ 0

	NATO	€ 45,921	€ 0	-€ 1,807	€ 9,910	€ 0
	EC	€ 41,107	€ 0	-€ 6,076	€ 22,860	€ 0
	UN	€ 50,294	€ 0	-€ 11,471	€ 1,568	€ 0
6	NL	€ 52,313	€ 0	-€ 15,820	€ 0	€ 0
	DE	€ 57,876	€ 1,704	-€ 10,978	€ 0	€ 0
	FR	€ 35,244	€ 0	-€ 6,589	€ 0	€ 0
	OECD	€ 43,057	€ 0	-€ 194	€ 2,855	€ 0
	CoE	€ 44,305	€ 0	-€ 191	€ 2,937	€ 0
	NATO	€ 46,978	€ 0	-€ 1,644	€ 3,115	€ 0
	EC	€ 67,365	€ 0	-€ 13,113	€ 3,570	€ 0
	UN	€ 55,274	€ 0	-€ 12,782	€ 1,568	€ 0
	NL	€ 37,305	€ 0	-€ 10,518	€ 0	€ 0
	DE	€ 49,765	€ 0	-€ 12,893	€ 0	€ 0
FR	€ 27,530	€ 0	-€ 5,097	€ 0	€ 0	
OECD	€ 42,536	€ 0	-€ 191	€ 0	€ 0	
CoE	€ 43,720	€ 0	-€ 188	€ 0	€ 0	
NATO	€ 44,077	€ 0	-€ 1,543	€ 0	€ 0	
EC	€ 46,510	€ 0	-€ 7,247	€ 0	€ 0	
UN	€ 69,426	€ 0	-€ 16,031	€ 0	€ 0	
8	NL	€ 59,438	€ 0	-€ 17,863	€ 1,732	€ 0
	DE	€ 57,574	€ 4,511	-€ 11,861	€ 4,781	€ 0
	FR	€ 43,006	€ 1,174	-€ 8,512	€ 0	€ 0
	OECD	€ 54,353	€ 0	-€ 245	€ 10,581	€ 0
	CoE	€ 55,926	€ 0	-€ 240	€ 9,782	€ 0
	NATO	€ 56,328	€ 0	-€ 1,971	€ 10,589	€ 0
	EC	€ 67,365	€ 0	-€ 13,113	€ 23,454	€ 0
	UN	€ 88,955	€ 0	-€ 21,936	€ 5,377	€ 0
9	NL	€ 66,991	€ 0	-€ 23,398	€ 0	€ 0
	DE	€ 69,840	€ 1,704	-€ 15,077	€ 0	€ 0
	FR	€ 71,511	€ 0	-€ 20,064	€ 0	€ 0
	OECD	€ 72,579	€ 0	-€ 327	€ 4,812	€ 0
	CoE	€ 72,741	€ 0	-€ 313	€ 4,823	€ 0
	NATO	€ 74,144	€ 0	-€ 2,595	€ 4,916	€ 0
	EC	€ 110,395	€ 0	-€ 32,081	€ 4,544	€ 0
	UN	€ 117,177	€ 0	-€ 30,611	€ 7,433	€ 0
10	NL	€ 59,438	€ 0	-€ 17,863	€ 1,732	€ 0
	DE	€ 91,284	€ 4,511	-€ 24,255	€ 4,781	€ 0
	FR	€ 62,723	€ 1,174	-€ 15,674	€ 0	€ 0
	OECD	€ 77,938	€ 0	-€ 351	€ 12,142	€ 0
	CoE	€ 80,193	€ 0	-€ 345	€ 11,387	€ 0
	NATO	€ 80,764	€ 0	-€ 2,827	€ 12,183	€ 0
	EC	€ 86,236	€ 0	-€ 20,398	€ 23,881	€ 0

	UN	€ 151,270	€ 0	-€ 43,091	€ 9,919	€ 0
	NL	€ 82,048	€ 0	-€ 31,830	€ 0	€ 0
	DE	€ 98,860	€ 1,704	-€ 25,305	€ 0	€ 0
	FR	€ 113,558	€ 0	-€ 39,550	€ 0	€ 0
11	OECD	€ 105,199	€ 0	-€ 473	€ 6,975	€ 0
	CoE	€ 103,048	€ 0	-€ 443	€ 6,832	€ 0
	NATO	€ 108,748	€ 0	-€ 3,808	€ 7,210	€ 0
	EC	€ 124,905	€ 0	-€ 39,097	€ 4,872	€ 0
	UN	€ 178,229	€ 0	-€ 53,545	€ 12,902	€ 0

Source: SEO analysis

Note: All amounts are in euros, corrected for purchasing power parity so that each euro has the same acquisitive power in the country of employment as it does in Belgium. Tax contribution includes social security contributions where applicable. The gross annual salary listed in this table is after payment of the pension contribution. Only German and French civil servants pay taxes over their family allowance. In some cases, the family and children's allowance is a combination of multiple allowances. Similarly, the expat allowance listed in the table can be a combination of expat allowances for the employees as well as their family members (if applicable). The net annual income is the sum of all amounts.

Image 9 - Decomposition of annual net income at current level for each reference person and employer

Suggested remuneration

As shown in the tables above, the level of remuneration is very different from an organisation to another. Answering to the question what is the ideal and fair remuneration in an organisation is very difficult. There are so many factors to consider: national and local standards, cost of life, law of supply and demand, sector of activity, legal regulations, attractiveness, level of taxation, bonuses, health insurance, pension plan, etc.

Trying to compare level of remunerations in organisations based in different countries working in different sector is, to say the least, a very difficult objective and based on many assumptions. The suggested range of remuneration that we formulate at this point in time should be considered with great precaution and should be discussed with the budget planner.

Considering that the central office will be located in Florence, Italy, the following level of remuneration could be suggested depending on the level of experience, education and responsibilities (gross salary without employer's contributions):

- Director General: 75k€ - 95k€
- Deputy Director: 60k€ - 80k€
- Head of office: 50k€ - 70k€
- Head of unit: 35k€ - 55k€
- Assistant: 20k€ - 40k€

Difference of remuneration could be also be made between the different heads of unit or assistants, depending on the degree expected (Bachelor, Master, PhD), the level of responsibilities and the complexity of their tasks.

4.2 Employee benefits

In addition to an attractive salary policy, a procedure to attract and retain highly talented employees is to use perquisites, a benefit received in addition to a regular salary. The nature or the value of perquisites may differ from one ERIC to another, according to national rules, the size of the ERIC or its human resources policy. This report is not intended to list all of the perquisites that an employee may receive but to provide an overview of those that are used in some ERICs and that could be employed by E-RIHS to reward all or part of its employees. It is important, however, to maintain a certain balance of remuneration within an organization so as not to create excessive pay gaps between its members. Furthermore, a perquisite policy should be designed in accordance with existing national legislation and with national or sectoral collective-bargaining agreements.

Contribution to costs for relocation

This instrument covers fully or partially the moving expenses of an employee who settles in a new city/country for his or her work. Moving to another country has a different impact on an employee depending on his or her age, position and marital status. Often, moving abroad is not an individual decision but should consider familial constraints. If the employee has a family, this decision requires not only finding a new place to live but also a school for the children and compensating the fact that the partner has to leave his or her job. For example, the European Spallation Source (ESS) ERIC offers an extensive relocation package²⁵ which offers help throughout the process.

Healthcare plans

Although the possibilities are very different from one country to another, depending on the national healthcare system in place, it is often possible to provide employees with a complement to the basic health coverage. Thus, he or she can be covered for health expenses that are not covered by basic health insurance - to which he or she normally contributes through his or her salary - such as dental or optical expenses.

Retirement benefits

An interesting initiative at the EU level on employer-sponsored pension savings for people moving between countries is **RESAVER**. A research infrastructure as E-RIHS is expected to attract staff from all over Europe and beyond. The lack of uniformity among countries with regard to retirement pensions may create obstacles to mobility. In that respect, the European Commission supported the creation of RESAVER, a cross-border occupational pension scheme tailored for European research organisations and their employees. It enables employees to stay with the same pension plan when moving between different countries or changing jobs. RESAVER will be articulated around three elements: a pension fund, an occupational pension insurance and a private pension insurance. At the beginning of 2019, the RESAVER consortium counted approximately 20 institutions in 11 countries. BBMRI is the only ERIC to have joined the consortium so far. Following the future developments of RESAVER and other pan-European initiatives on pensions funds, E-RIHS may decide in the future to join the consortium and benefit from an additional asset for attracting and retaining talented staff.

²⁵ <https://europeanspallationsource.se/careers/family-support#ff>

Transportation

As perquisite, an organization may decide to fund all or part of an employee's transportation costs to the workplace. That could be the reimbursement of a public transportation pass, a grant for the purchase of a bicycle or an electric bicycle, a lump sum for the gasoline costs or even the provision of a vehicle for personal use.

Education and training

Training is not or should not be considered an employee benefit. Rather, it should be the duty, at least moral and strategic, of the employer in order to have an educated staff able to adapt to change and seize opportunities. Moreover, in a number of European countries, continuing education and training is compulsory. However, what can attract and retain employees is the training budget available to them. It is a strong incentive to be part of an organisation offering quality and tailored training and education.

5 Evaluation

An evaluation system makes it possible to gather the information needed to build the various programmes (promotion, remuneration, training, etc.) and to base decisions on the careers of staff members.

Setting up an evaluation system can serve two purposes:

- to improve communication between management and staff, and to create a positive work environment;
- to make more rational decisions and to allow the definition of professional projects.

A well-defined evaluation system allows to take better decisions for the organisation in terms of:

- Promotions, transfers, changes of assignment;
- Actions to improve capacity and organisation (training, etc.);
- Remuneration adjustment.

Evaluation systems are of great interest to the organisation but also to the employee. For the organisation, they enable to monitor the operational aspect (monitoring the contribution of each individual to the achievement of objectives), the control of employment policy (knowing the potential of current and future skills), the control of hierarchy and structure (identifying dysfunctions, improving the information system). Following the feedback of the evaluation, the employee shall be able to improve his work, his autonomy, his competence but also express his thoughts and ideas or be aware of the opportunities offered by the organisation. The employee shall be able to express as well his or her difficulties and dissatisfactions, his or her wishes for development, training and career.

In order to give a practical dimension to this part, we **have developed an evaluation grid which can be found in [Appendix 2](#)**.

6 Motivation

A research infrastructure should not only be able to attract and recruit good staff, but the most important challenge it is to retain valuable personnel over time. Ensuring that the right people are at the right place at the right time requires that external (education and training, mobility support, greater harmonisation at EU level ²⁶) and internal factors are met. These are multi-faceted, it could be security on the workplace (although it does not much concern E-RIHS), health and well-being, work conditions or diversity and interest of the position. One important driver which impacts the behaviour and the performance of an employee is the motivation. Fostering and nurturing the motivation is one of the most important tasks of a research infrastructure should strive for in order to retain talents in the organisation.

6.1 Theory

Staff competence and motivation are key factors for the successful implementation of an ERIC. Motivation is derived from the Latin word “movere”, to move. Motivation is an internal force, based on individual needs and expectations which drives someone to do something. A well-known academic theory was developed by the psychologist Frederick Herzberg, the **two-factor theory**.

According to the Herzberg’s findings, satisfaction at work is highly dependent on *motivators*, while dissatisfaction is associated with *hygiene factors*. Motivators are intrinsic to the job, i.e. the belong to the position. Herzberg identified six of them: advancement, recognition, work itself, responsibility, possibility of growth and achievement. These six factors work contribute greatly to the job satisfaction but have very little impact on the job dissatisfaction.

On the other hand, hygiene factors are contingent, extrinsic to the job. Herzberg found eight hygiene factors in his research: salary, interpersonal relations, supervision, company/policy administration, working conditions, personal life, status, job security. Hygiene factors prevent dissatisfaction but, nevertheless, they do not lead to motivation.

This theory has been criticized over the time for different reasons. For example, the distinction between some motivators and hygiene factors are disputed, in particular the salary considered by some more intrinsic than extrinsic to the position. Furthermore, the theory seems valid if applied to some specific industries but makes less sense for others. A description for each category of the Herzberg’s two-factor theory is shown below:

	Motivators	Description
1	Achievement	Successful performance of individual’s work tasks, solving problems, justification and seeing the results of one’s work
2	Recognition	Notice, praise and criticism received from colleagues or management

²⁶ ESFRI Long-Term Sustainability Working Group (2017), Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures, Dipartimento di Fisica - Università degli Studi di Milano, p. 24.

3	Responsibility	Sense of responsibility given to an employee for his/her own work or being given new responsibilities
4	Work itself	Actual content of the job
5	Advancement	Change in one's position at work, promotion
6	Possibility of growth	Possibility to enhance knowledge and develop through job experience

	Hygiene factors	Description
1	Salary	Economic benefit for work
2	Interpersonal relations	Coworkers relations
3	Supervision	Behaviour of managers towards employees
4	Company policy/administration	Organisational management at workplaces
5	Working conditions	Physical environment of working and available facilities
6	Personal life	Relationship with other members of the family, composition of the family, life-style...
7	Status	Job titles, symbols of rank and position
8	Job security	Probability that an individual will keep their job

Motivation and job satisfaction may sound similar, however they are not synonyms. Motivation is a process that triggers behaviour, while satisfaction is an attitude, an emotional response. In short, an employee may be satisfied with the job but not motivated. Nevertheless, we can invert this reasoning: a motivated employee will be more likely satisfied and will better perform at work.

Motivation may be intrinsic and extrinsic. Intrinsic motivation *“occurs when we act without any obvious external rewards. We simply enjoy an activity or see it as an opportunity to explore, learn, and actualize our potentials.”*²⁷ Extrinsic motivation refers to *“our tendency to perform activities for known external rewards, whether they be tangible (e.g., money) or psychological (e.g., praise) in nature”*.²⁸

Another well-known theory, the hierarchy of needs, has been conceptualised by Abraham Maslow in 1943 in his paper *“A Theory of Human Motivation”* published in the *Psychological Review*. The theory outlined five hierarchical needs. These are shaped into a pyramid in which most fundamental needs are at the bottom. Once lower level needs are satisfied, higher level needs can be addressed. The pyramid is shown below:

²⁷ Coon D.; Mitterer J. O. (2010). Introduction to psychology: Gateways to mind and behavior with concept maps. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth.

²⁸ Brown L. V. (2007). Psychology of motivation. New York: Nova Publishers.

Image 10 - Maslow's hierarchy of needs

This theory has not been specifically proposed for being applied to organisations and employees' performances, even though later studies had proven its appropriateness. In the original theory, these five levels are described as follows:

Physiological needs: It refers to most basic and strongest biological needs, like food, water, oxygen, sleep, homeostasis. If translated to a research infrastructure, we could indicate at this level a salary, good working conditions and decent working space, i.e. sufficient light, clean premises, a computer, internet, etc.

Safety needs: Once physiological needs are satisfied, safety needs take precedence and influence the behaviour. These includes personal, emotional, financial and health security. In an organisation it could be applied as follows: safe working environment, attractive salary, fringe benefits, pension schemes, permanent working contracts.

Needs for love, affection and belongingness: When safety needs are satisfied, the next class of needs emerge and guide the behaviour. This involves the need of giving and receiving love, affection and the sense of belonging. In RIs, these needs could be satisfied by belonging to a functional organisation or a team, having good co-workers relationships, being part of a research community, networking, having a good work-life balance.

Needs for esteem: Once the third level has been satisfied, the need for esteem can become dominant, involving the needs for both self-esteem and esteem. Status, recognition, fame, prestige, and attention are associated with this level of the pyramid. Within a RI, this may refer to career advancements, positive feedbacks, (social) recognition, being esteemed by the research community, being invited to speak at conferences, review panels, being asked to lead projects or work packages.

Needs for self-actualisation: When precedent levels are satisfied, the last level of the pyramid – the needs for self-actualisation – comes into play. Self-actualisation describes the realisation of full potential, summarised by Maslow as *"What a man can be, he must be"*. It involves the possibility of fully exploiting one's own abilities and talents. In RIs, this may involve creativity and innovation, autonomy to run one's own projects.

Difference between reward and motivation

The difference between motivation and reward is that generally, the motivation comes before the behaviour, while the reward comes after. Motivation and reward are nonetheless intertwined. Reward can be defined as what an individual receives for doing something rather than the reason for doing it. Rewards policies are processes, policies and strategies to motivate subjects to achieve strategic goals and enhance the productivity and efficiency of organisations. A well-organised reward system is important to motivate employees and support job satisfaction and commitment, leading to a better performance of employees. A reward system should not only focus on salaries and benefits but also on non-financial rewards such as empowerment, recognition, reputation, trust, increased responsibilities. The ultimate objective is to increase productivity and performance by increasing employee's willingness to work.

In public administration studies rewards can be categorised in measurable and unmeasurable²⁹ terms. Measurable rewards are tangible elements measured through monetary units and/or other units of the metric system. The impact of financial rewards in the public sector is much lower than in the private for two reasons. First, the public sector cannot offer important incentives and bonuses on the contrary to the private sector. Secondly, employees in the public sector tend to be intrinsically more motivated than the ones in the private sector. This is particularly true in the research environment, people "work for science", to contribute to the global knowledge rather than for money. Unmeasurable rewards are intangible elements difficult to measure such as job responsibilities and professionalism.

The nature of rewards can be intrinsic or extrinsic. Intrinsic rewards exist in the job itself and give personal satisfaction to individuals. In these respect, intrinsic rewards are related to autonomy, empowerment, trust, etc. Intrinsic rewards tend to generate positive effects on job involvement. Extrinsic rewards are tangible and visible rewards given to individuals for achieving goals. For example, a pay raise, fringe benefits, promotion, etc. A good balance between intrinsic and extrinsic rewards is necessary. Studies suggested that intrinsic rewards are related to affective commitment, job involvement and motivation, while extrinsic rewards are more prominent as to continuing commitment to the organisation. Overall, in the public sector and mission-oriented organisations, studies tend to show that extrinsic rewards may erode intrinsic motivation.

The objective of a motivation strategy is to increase the effective contribution of employees of the organisation in achieving its mission. As described above, motivation is affected by numerous factors. Nevertheless, the quality of the leadership plays an important role as well. In this respect, the appointment and training of good leaders – in the case of E-RIHS, the Directors but also the Head of Office or the Heads of Units when they are managing assistants – are crucial and should be integrated in the human resources strategy³⁰.

6.2 Motivation strategies in E-RIHS

Human resources management is a complex process that requires solid supporting strategies to be efficient and should pay particular attention to the specificity of a research infrastructure whose

²⁹ Coccia M., Benati I. (2018). Rewards in public administration: A proposed classification. 5. 68-80. 10.1453/jsas.v5i2.1648.

³⁰ Armstrong M., (2006), Human Resource Management Practice, Kogan Page, Pp 251-269.

mission is to enable excellent science and to offer cutting-edge technologies, tools and services to users.

In addition to motivation and rewards theories, it is interesting, in order to develop an adequate motivation strategy for E-RIHS, to look at the six key work practises as identified by Purcell *et al* (2003) in a study commissioned by the CIPD (Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development) in the UK. Findings revealed that a combination of these six work practises will contribute to improve performance and motivation. In order of importance, we list the key work practises below:

Career development and opportunities for advancement

In terms of motivation, career progression and career development are essential. Career progression does not only include the notion of promotion, but rather a series of measures to implement in the work context such as granting more autonomy to the employees, varying the tasks and activities for a given position or develop opportunities to acquire new competencies. For example, horizontal and external mobility, as shown in section 10 can be encouraged.

Training opportunities

Training is the use of systematic and planned instruction and development activities to promote learning³¹. Training opportunities are important to enhance staff commitment and tend to result in a more efficient organisation if based on an objective assessment of need.

Job influence and challenge

Job satisfaction can be increased when employees have some influence on how they do their job and when they have opportunities to face interesting challenges. As a result, the way a position is defined, the scope of activities an employee should carry out and their variety influence the job satisfaction. Job rotation, job enlargement, job enrichment or the creation of self-managed teams are techniques that can be used in this area.

Involvement and communication

This practice includes two different interrelated aspects. Involvement refers to the opportunity to contribute to decisions. Encouraging involvement often results in a higher level of satisfaction towards the management of an organisation. At the same time, effective communication is a vital part of the process, for which a solid knowledge management policy has to be developed.

Performance management and appraisal processes

Underperformance is often indicated as a source of dissatisfaction among employees. However, it is crucial to clarify what constitute an acceptable level of performance. It is also suggested that performance reviews should focus on performance planning and development rather than retrospective assessment. Another interesting aspect of the study concerns the importance of properly implementing a human resource policy, which is endorsed by the personnel. Employees

³¹ O’Riordan (2017), The practise of Human Resource Management, Institute of Public Administration.

tend to have a negative attitude over poorly applied HR policies rather than the absence of a particular policy.

□ **Work-life balance**

Work-life balance emerges as an important area for increasing motivation and keep the employee in an organisation. Flexible working hours, telework arrangements, family friendly policies might be a partial solution to deal with pressure employees might face, inside and outside of work. In that area, an employer shall pay particular attention to the existing national legislation and collective labour agreements of the sector. An employer that will propose better work condition than the one fixed by the legislation has a great chance of increasing employee motivation.

To conclude, the study shows that what matters is *“the way people work together to be productive and flexible enough to meet new challenges”*³². This is facilitated by two key ingredients: organisational culture and the attitude of managers.

More than in purely “scientific/academic” contexts, research infrastructures need a workforce with varied skill sets, e.g. scientific staff, technical staff, administrative and support staff. Another key suggestion for a research infrastructure is to strive for parity of esteem between the diverse workforce: no specific sort of staff should be considered more important than the other.

³² Purcell J *et al* (2003), *Understanding the People and Performance Link*, CIPD: London, p.32.

7 Employee engagement

In 2013, the poll institute Gallup carried out a field survey on a sample of 73 700 employees located in 142 countries to measure employee engagement. The conclusion is striking: only 13% said they are “committed/engaged” (loyal and productive) in their work (only 9% in France!). 87% considered themselves disengaged (just putting in time) and among those, 24% are “actively disengaged” (unhappy and spreading their discontent).

Since a couple of years *engagement* have been a trend topic among leaders of organisation, human resources departments and scholars as well. There is a general sense of urgency to tackle that pitfall and many different approaches have been considered.

Contrary to popular misconception, engagement is not (only) about perquisites: like a company car for personal use, a supplementary pension or a pleasant work atmosphere with foosball tables, fresh fruits and massages. Perquisites can help attracting people to work for an organisation instead of another or rewarding them for the work done but fostering intrinsic personal satisfaction and motivation is what really drives employee engagement. Fleming and Asplund describe employee engagement as, “*the ability to capture the heads, hearts, and souls of your employees to instill an intrinsic desire and passion for excellence*”³³.

Engagement can be foster through the structure and values of the organisation, like transparency and autonomy but also through the freedom and quality of relationships between the employees and the top management. Here are some key words that are crucial to support engagement in an organisation:

Autonomy. People tend to support what they help create. This is why the structure of the organisation is important, especially when it comes to the decision-making process. If employees are involved from the beginning in shaping a project, if they are able to take their own decision, confront them with the reality on the ground, adapt their course of actions autonomously until the successful completion of the project, it will most probably give them a feeling of belonging, ownership and fulfilment. Top-down decisions are often badly perceived, because disconnected from the field reality in which the employee is evolving. Autonomy on the contrary strongly increases the employees' feeling of empowerment.

Transparency. The organisation should follow an open-book policy: no details, financials included, should be hidden from employees, so everyone could know the situation of an organisation and where it is heading toward. Information is shared with everyone in real time even sensitive one. Transparency help employees to understand the context and more importantly how their own effort could help the organisation achieve its goals.

Personal development. Supporting the own career goals of employees is an important lever for engagement. People have a real hunger for knowledge and it's the role of the management to support it, even if at first glance it might not directly useful for the organisation. Every form of knowledge might prove useful in a way or another. Training and curiosity are essential components for the success of an organisation and should be encourage continuously. Nurturing individual strengths is a fruitful investment both for the organisation that can rely on new competences, ideas, skills to overcome obstacles and achieve its goals as well as for the people who will develop a greater sense of engagement toward an organisation that take their will, aspirations and strengths into consideration and foster them.

³³ Fleming J.H., Asplund J. (2007). Human Sigma. New York; Gallup Press, p. 2

8 Training

Offering access to measures for the continuing development of skills and competencies are extremely important for an organisation and to prepare staff to respond and adapt to different challenges that may occur over the lifetime of a research infrastructure. In 2005, the European Commission published a Charter for the Employment of researcher and Code of Conduct³⁴ which states that *“employers and/or funders should ensure that all researchers at any stage of their career, regardless of their contractual situation, are given the opportunity for professional development and for improving their employability through access to measures for the continuing development of skills and competencies. Such measures should be regularly assessed for their accessibility, take-up and effectiveness in improving competencies, skills and employability”*.

However, continuing professional development should not be solely oriented to scientific staff. Therefore, the RI should promote and communicate opportunities to develop new understandings and skills for all staff categories involved and allocate the budget and time for staff learning. National nodes can also offer opportunities in that regard.

Moreover, a research infrastructure needs a diverse workforce and it is particularly important that scientific staff is encouraged to learn soft skills (communication, project management, management) or learn technical skills, while technical and administrative staff should be encouraged to learn or “absorb” the science.

It has been shown above that the quality of leadership plays an important role and training and development should be encouraged in this respect. Therefore, we present below the project RITrain aimed at training current and future managers of world-class research infrastructures.

RITrain

Running research infrastructures requires a set of specific skills that are susceptible of being adapted throughout the different phases of an ERIC (planning, construction, operation). There is a limited number of people who have experience in running intergovernmental research organisations and training future managers became a priority for ensuring long-term sustainability of Research Infrastructures³⁵.

RITrain, the Research Infrastructure Training Programme, is the answer to this growing need. RITrain received funding from the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 programme with the objective of improving and professionalizing the training of managerial and leadership staff in research infrastructures. The vision is to form the next generation of executives of RIs and prepare them with state-of-the-art managerial and leadership skills tailored to scientific services providers.

The project coordinated by BBMRI ERIC runs from September 2015 to August 2019 and the consortium is mostly composed of research infrastructures. RITrain is structured around three interlinked service offering:

- an Executive Master

³⁴ European Commission, Directorate-General for Research (2005), The European Charter for Researchers, The Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers, Brussels, p. 15.

³⁵ ESFRI Long-Term Sustainability Working Group (2017), Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures, Dipartimento di Fisica - Università degli Studi di Milano, p. 26.

- a series of webinars
- Knowledge and staff exchanges

The Executive Master is organised in collaboration with the University of Milano-Bicocca and is specifically tailored to the specific needs of the research infrastructures. The structure of the Master is compliant with the standards set out by the Bologna process and is organised over 60 ECTS. The Master targets professionals working in RIs (Director Generals, Chief Operating Officers, Unit Heads, middle management) or other professional wishing to enhance their capacities in managing RIs (Head of National Nodes, representatives of funding agencies and Ministries in relation with RIs). Modules capture what actual needs of managing a RIs are: strategic management, financial management, leadership and team building, business development and innovation with an eye on planning and setting up new infrastructures. The first edition of the Master started in September 2017 and ended in March 2019, while the second edition began at the end of 2018 and will end in 2020.

Another interesting training area developed by RITrain is a series of webinars featured by RIs experts on a specific challenge. Those webinars are usually 20-30 minutes long and they organised in the form of an interview or a lecture. Topics may vary from governing issues to ethics management.

Furthermore, another integrative part of the Executive Master is centred around staff exchanges to further enhance the continuous professional development of RIs managers. The last two events in 2018 focused on Equality, Diversity, Inclusion and Project Management.

The benefits of participating to RITrain activities are not only related to acquiring competencies that are necessary to run a research infrastructure, but also to meet RIs staff to see what are the similarities and differences, which common challenges RIs face and which specific solutions are adopted. RITrain might be an interesting training opportunity for E-RIHS and it is suggested to keep an eye on future activities developed in this respect.

10 Advancement and Career

Mobility should be encouraged, both internally and externally. In medium-small highly specialised research infrastructures, upward mobility can be difficult to achieve, especially if there is not a consistent staff turnover.

Horizontal (or internal) mobility allows employees to have the chance to work in various teams throughout an organisation. With this approach, staff is involved in new projects, activities, administrative and technical challenges and can grow its skills and be more versatile. Sometimes, internal mobility may arise from different organisational change processes (change of strategic/business plan, innovation etc.). E-RIHS is designed to provide access to a wide range of forefront scientific infrastructure, methodologies, data and tools etc. through four integrated platforms: ARCHLAB, DIGILAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB. Rather than following a strict hierarchy behind those divisions, a more fluid structure is therefore suggested. We also suggest to consider flexible pathways between research, management and technician roles, the limits of certain very specific competences.

However, an ERIC is a complex network composed of a variety of users, stakeholders, researchers, national institutions, funders. **External mobility** helps to connect different parts of the organisation. This could be achieved in different ways. Here we suggest an interesting instrument used by CLARIN: the CLARIN Mobility Grants. These grants allow researchers and developers to fund, up to 1.000€, short visits (usually a week) between representatives of CLARIN sites to collaborate on building and using the CLARIN infrastructure. The aim is focused on sharing of expertise between CLARIN centres and countries and integration of resources, tools and services. This enhances integration within the organisation at the human resources level and encourages a sort of horizontal/external mobility between CLARIN centres in different countries and vertical mobility between CLARIN centres on the one hand, and humanities or social sciences research institutes (not necessarily CLARIN centres) across Europe on the other. Mobility is intended for technical and scientific staff, experts and scholars to provide or receive training or collaborate. CLARIN Mobility Grants are continuous and the decision for funding is usually taken in a couple of weeks. This instrument could be reproduced, perhaps in a bigger scale, in E-RIHS, considering the specificities and different needs of both infrastructures.

11 Critical risks

We have identified a set of 9 critical risks likely to have a negative impact on the human resources policy within E-RIHS. The risks can be of different kinds: organisational, motivational, behavioural and financial.

	Critical risk	Mitigation measures
1	Temporary or permanent lack of information or know-how due to personnel prolonged absence or changing jobs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure that information or know-how is documented and shared among at least two persons. - Keep extensive and up-to date documentation. - Timely information or knowledge transfer to other personnel members.
2	Commitment of one or more Members stops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is extremely unlikely that the ERIC runs out of funding at once. However, it is suggested to prepare in advance sustainability plans with different scenarios, considering possible adjustment of the governance of the infrastructure.
3	Difficulties in recruiting and retaining specialised staff.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Check if the salary and work conditions are attractive enough. - Second personnel from national nodes or outsource. - Build a solid network around training and education activities carried out by the ERIC.
4	Poor alignment of HR strategy with strategic plan and/or mission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strategic plans and mission should be coherently designed on the basis of the competence and skills of the staff.
5	Ineffective selection processes resulting in poor hiring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Set up internal rules or guidelines for constituting selection committees - Ensure that minimum requirements and the expected skills in the job description do not lead to inconsistent applications and check if the job advertisement has been correctly disseminated. - Ensure that the selection committee is diverse in its composition and includes middle management employees relevant for the position.

6	Employee engagement is low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure that autonomy, transparency and personal development are effectively implemented in the organisational culture.
7	Excessive turnover	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Outline clear career paths. - Increase internal or external mobility, offer training measures to improve skills. - Improve recruiting processes. - Rethink organisational culture.
8	Acceptable work-life balance of employees is not met (e.g. excessive stress, burnouts)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Apply family-friendly policies and allow flexible working hours and telework arrangements. - Conduct regular appraisal and mentoring schemes. - Ensure that too much pressure is not falling on individuals (overwork, excessive amount of business travels). - Give support to foreign staff and possibly their families for a quick adaptation.
9	Unethical behaviour (disclosure of confidential information, misrepresentation of activities, misuse of equipment or facilities, sexual harassment, illegal acts)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Take appropriate measures according to the seriousness of the conduct or if behaviour does not change. - Improve workplace culture. - Avoid isolation and alienation that might lead to antagonistic feelings and behaviours. - Introduce a Code of Conduct. - Elect an employee of the organisation in charge of harassment that report to the direction.

Conclusion

To conclude this report, we would like to highlight one last important message that was underlined throughout the different sections: People are at the heart of every organisation. It may sound like a commonplace but it is nevertheless true. On that subject, the RAMIRI handbook has a very clear statement: *“A number of issues – legal, governance, financial, management, etc. – have a bearing on the establishment and management of a research infrastructure. All of them are important and need to be considered with much care and in considerable detail. But the role played ultimately by people underlies all these factors, and indeed goes to the heart of the effective success of an RI”*.

At this particularly point in time, it is difficult to evaluate the nature and the size of the future E-RIHS ERIC central office. A number of factors come into play, first of all the budget that will be allocated to the organization, but also the number and scope of its activities, the relations with national nodes, etc. As a consequence, defining a sound human resources policy is a difficult exercise. However, it is also the hallmark of this type of report to put forward a set of recommendations, proposals to help E-RIHS attract and retain talents, make sure they feel welcome and motivated to carry out their activities in the most effective and efficient way.

No matter how small or large, simple or complex the future E-RIHS ERIC will be, having a structured and sound human resources policy will be of great help, both for the organisation and its future employees. And we hope that recommendations and guidelines given in this document will contribute to it.

Annex 1: Organisational chart of E-RIHS

Annex 2: Practical guide for an annual review

Practical guide for an annual review

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Personal details

Staff member name:

Job title:

Weekly working time:

Starting date of the contract:

Current pay scale:

Line manager name:

Review meeting date:

Last review meeting date:

Names of the persons conducting the interview:

Type of review (probation, annual, etc.):

Overall job description (to be filled in by the line manager):

Self-evaluation

Description of your activities in the past year:

Self-evaluation of your interpersonal skills:

	low	average	good	strong	Not relevant
Being with others					
Ability to work in a team					
Listening					
Mentoring - Teaching and helping others how to do something					
Coordination - Adjusting actions in relation to others' actions					
Ability to adapt to change					

Negotiation - Discussion aimed at reaching an agreement.					
Sense of commitment and responsibility					
Social Perceptiveness - Being aware of others' reactions					
Energy and enthusiasm					
Individual skills					
Analytical skills					
Autonomy					
Accuracy and attention to details					
Initiative-oriented					
Creativity					
Responsiveness					
Anticipation					
Time management					
Leadership skills					
Reporting					

Performance Appraisal

Please rate the employee's performance against the following competencies, concluding with the overall rating for this Probation Review.

If the competency is not relevant, please select 'Not relevant to the role'.

If you indicate at least one or more ratings that are 'Below Expectations', please see Section F. Poor Performance.

Ratings Description

1	<i>Below Expectations</i>	<i>Performing in some areas only, needs significant improvement to achieve the required standard. There are weaknesses apparent in the performance of the candidate which can/cannot be overcome at this time.</i>
2	<i>Met Expectations</i>	<i>Good performance, all objectives were delivered and expectations were met to the required standard. Overall staff member is effective in the role.</i>
3	<i>Expectations met at high standard</i>	<i>Very good performance, candidate performing very well to a noticeably good quality, with a high level of output to a high standard.</i>
4	<i>Not relevant to the role</i>	<i>Competency is not relevant to the role.</i>

Personal Qualities

Competency:	Time Keeping	
Competency Description:	Adheres to the time-keeping and attendance requirements of the section as outlined in the employment contract; prompt /on-time for required meetings	
Rating:	1. Below Expectations	
	2. Met Expectations	
	3. Expectations met at High Standard	
	4. Not relevant to the role	
Line Manager Comments:		
Employee Comments:		

Competency:	Motivation, Interest and Flexibility	
Competency Description:	Shows interest in the job. Can be trusted to work independently and unsupervised. Willing to listen and carry out instructions. Adaptable to the requirements of the post, shows commitment to the job and team members at all times.	
Rating:	1. Below Expectations	
	2. Met Expectations	
	3. Expectations met at High Standard	
	4. Not relevant to the role	
Line Manager Comments:		
Employee Comments:		

Competency:	Initiative and openness to learning	
Competency Description:	Adaptable to the requirements of the post, shows commitment to the job and team members at all times. Demonstrates willingness to learn. Looks to participate in training – quick learner.	
Rating:	1. Below Expectations	
	2. Met Expectations	
	3. Expectations met at High Standard	
	4. Not relevant to the role	
Line Manager Comments:		
Employee Comments:		

Communication Skills/Interpersonal Skills

Competency:	Communication Skills /Interpersonal Skills	
Competency Description:	Effectively communicates to provide information, clear and concise, gains understanding and maintains effective working relationships. Demonstrates good manners and politeness even in potentially difficult situations. Comfortable in liaising with people within and outside of team.	
Rating:	1. Below Expectations	
	2. Met Expectations	
	3. Expectations met at High Standard	
	4. Not relevant to the role	
Line Manager Comments:		
Employee Comments:		

Competency:	Team Work	
Competency Description:	Works co-operatively with others on the team. Supportive of other team members	
Rating:	1. Below Expectations	
	2. Met Expectations	
	3. Expectations met at High Standard	
	4. Not relevant to the role	
Line Manager Comments:		
Employee Comments:		

Competency:	Conscientiousness	
Competency Description:	Focuses on getting things finished, persists until the job is completed	
Rating:	1. Below Expectations	
	2. Met Expectations	
	3. Expectations met at High Standard	
	4. Not relevant to the role	
Line Manager Comments:		
Employee Comments:		

Competency:	Attention to Detail	
Competency Description:	Thorough in accomplishing a task with concern for all the areas involved (no matter how small). Performs routine or repetitious tasks with care and attention.	
Rating:	1. Below Expectations	
	2. Met Expectations	
	3. Expectations met at High Standard	
	4. Not relevant to the role	
Line Manager Comments:		
Employee Comments:		

Specific Skills

Please insert any additional skills/competencies that are required of the candidate. The comments box can include consistent highlights of performance, or persistent issues.

For example:

- Leadership Skills
- Management Skills
- Supervisory Skills
- Candidate to implement ...
- Candidate to develop/design ...

Role Specific Goal/Skills	Rating	Line Manager comment	Employee Comment

Objectives review

Assessment of the achievement of the goals (objectives, projects, etc.) defined the previous year:

Objective 1:	Title objective	
Objective Description:	XXXX.	
Rating:	1. Below Expectations	
	2. Met Expectations	
	3. Expectations met at High Standard	x
Line Manager Comments:		
Employee Comments:		

Objective 2:	Title objective	
Objective Description:	XXXX.	
Rating:	1. Below Expectations	
	2. Met Expectations	
	3. Expectations met at High Standard	x
Line Manager Comments:		
Employee Comments:		

Objective n:	Title objective	
Objective Description:	XXXX.	
Rating:	1. Below Expectations	
	2. Met Expectations	
	3. Expectations met at High Standard	x
Line Manager Comments:		

Employee Comments:	
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Expectations for the coming year

Objectives

Assessment of the achievement of the goals (objectives, projects, etc.) defined the previous year:

Objective 1:	Title objective
Objective Description:	XXXX.
Action plan:	
Framework (timing, etc.):	
Conditions for success:	

Objective 2:	Title objective
Objective Description:	XXXX.
Action plan:	
Framework (timing, etc.):	
Conditions for success:	

Objective 3:	Title objective
Objective Description:	XXXX.
Action plan:	
Framework (timing, etc.):	

Conditions for success:	
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Training

The training courses planned last year were:

- Training 1:
- Training 2:
- Training 3:

Have they been achieved?

Have the training courses met expectations and been successfully used in the workplace?

According to the employee, the training needs for the coming year are:

- Training 1:
- Training 2:
- Training 3:

According to the line manager, the training needs for the coming year are:

- Training 1:
- Training 2:
- Training 3:

Comments:

Career development

How would you like your position to evolve? (working conditions, work organization, task enrichment...):

What career development do you imagine in the medium (1-2 years) and long term (more than 3 years)?

Concluding notes

Line Manager's Comments:	
Date:	
Line Manager's Signature:	

Employee's Comments:	
Date:	
Employee's Signature:	

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Abbreviations

BBMRI	Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure
CLARIN	Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure
ECTS	European Credit Transfer System
EHRI	European Holocaust Research Infrastructure
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
FTE	Full-Time Equivalent
HR	Human Resources
RAMIRI	Realising and Managing International Research Infrastructures
RI	Research Infrastructure
RITrain	Research Infrastructure Training Programme
SHARE	Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe
UK	United Kingdom

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